

 PlaceMUS^{XR}

VISUAL IDENTITY

VISUAL IDENTITY

VISUAL LANGUAGE

Key elements:

- Immersive photography (heritage & music)
- Gradient overlays (purple tones)
- Fluid wave graphics
- Clean modular layouts

The style blends emotion, technology and culture.

APPLICATIONS

The visual identity is applied across multiple touchpoints:

- Social media (posts, covers)
- Posters and event communication
- Website and digital interfaces

Consistency across these channels reinforces brand recognition.

VISUAL IDENTITY

BROCHURE MOCKUP

The brochure applies the PlaceMUS XR visual identity through a combination of immersive visuals, gradient overlays and clean layouts. Graphic elements inspired by sound waves create continuity, while typography ensures clarity and accessibility.

BROCHURE MOCKUP

01 THE EXPERIENCE

THE EXPERIENCE UNFOLDS ACROSS 3 COMPLEMENTARY SCALES:

TERRITORIAL LEVEL
Interactive georeferenced cartography combining space, time, and semantic layers.

SITE LEVEL
Interactive 360° environments enriched with sonic and temporal dimensions.

DETAILED LEVEL
Immersive VR spaces with spatialised sound to explore architectural-acoustic relationships and emotional impact.

Accessibility and inclusivity are central: tools are designed for diverse audiences, including users with limited technical resources or disabilities.

IMPACTS 02

IMPACTS

PlaceMUS XR expands access to Europe's musical heritage and establishes sonic heritage as a fundamental research and cultural dimension.

The project generates **Impact across multiple sectors:**

- Museums and Cultural Institutions
- Creative and Cultural Industries
- Educational Institutions and Conservatories
- Tourism and Territorial Promotion
- Policymakers and Cultural Stakeholders

By complementing traditional visual approaches with listening-based experiences, PlaceMUS XR reveals **new layers of meaning rooted in soundscapes, narratives, and oral traditions.** Curators and designers can simulate exhibition layouts and sound diffusion strategies in virtual environments before physical implementation.

08 THE CONSORTIUM

ABOUT THE CONSORTIUM

PlaceMUS XR brings together a highly interdisciplinary consortium combining expertise in SSH and STEM domains: musicology, arts, ontology, acoustics, artificial intelligence, engineering, XR technologies, and digital storytelling.

The consortium includes:

Research Institutions **Universities** **Creative Industries** **Heritage Associations** **Cultural Foundations**

The project is coordinated by CNR – National Research Council of Italy, with partners from Italy, France, Poland, United Kingdom, Hungary and Georgia.

CONTACTS 09

CONTACTS

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LOGO ANIMATION

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SOCIAL MEDIA TAMPLATES

Social visuals use strong imagery combined with gradient overlays and bold typography.

Key principles:

- Clear focal point
- High contrast text
- Consistent logo placement

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Title Example

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Title Example

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PlaceMUS^{XR}

Title Example

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VISUAL IDENTITY

**BANNER
TAMPLATES**

VISUAL IDENTITY

